

Reviewer Acknowledgements

International Education Studies wishes to acknowledge the following individuals for their assistance with peer review of manuscripts for this issue. Their help and contributions in maintaining the quality of the journal are greatly appreciated.

International Education Studies is recruiting reviewers for the journal. If you are interested in becoming a reviewer, we welcome you to join us. Please contact us for the application form at: ies@ccsenet.org

Reviewers for Volume 14, Number 7

Alicia Cortes Wegner, University of Canterbury, New Zealand
Ana Isabel Santos, University of the Azores, Portugal
Annalisa Pavan, University of Padova, Italy
Charles Edward Notar, Jacksonville State University, USA
Chokri Kooli, International Center for Basic Research Applied, Canada
Gonzalo Almerich Cerveró, University of Valencia, Spain
Gregory M. Hauser, Roosevelt University, USA
Ibna Seraj Prodhon Mahbub, Sylhet International University, Bangladesh
Jamel Charaoui, Jeddah University, Saudi Arabia
Jong Eun Lee, Washington State University, USA
Julia Penn Shaw, State University of New York-Empire State College, USA
Muhammad Shahid Zulfiqar Ali, University of Education, Pakistan
Niknamian Soroush, Liberty University, USA
Pam Epler, Murray State University, USA
Rod Galloway, George Street Normal School, New Zealand
Roxanne Stevens, Azusa Pacific University, USA
Terra Gargano, American University, USA
Timo Lainema, University of Turku, Finland
Victor Wilburn, Southeast MO State University, USA